

Discussion #2 about SIR Model: Intra-area and Inter-area Components Relation

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1 SIR model for multiple area

From previous discussion [1] it is proposed that the SIR model can be advanced to consider the spatial aspect, in the form of

$$\frac{dS_i}{dt} = -\frac{1}{N_i} a_i S_i I_i - \mu_{ji}^S S_i + \mu_{ij}^S S_j, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dI_i}{dt} = \frac{1}{N_i} a_i S_i I_i - b_i I_i - \mu_{ji}^I I_i + \mu_{ij}^I I_j, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dR_i}{dt} = b_i I_i - \mu_{ji}^R R_i + \mu_{ij}^R R_j, \quad (3)$$

with μ_{ij}^X stands for mobility to X_i from X_j , where X can be $S, I,$ or R . The $a, b, S, I, R,$ and R_0 are the same as usual [2].

The world population is simply

$$N = \sum_{i=1}^{N_A} N_i = \sum_{i=1}^{N_A} S_i + \sum_{i=1}^{N_A} I_i + \sum_{i=1}^{N_A} R_i. \quad (4)$$

Number of area is stored in N_A . The term region in [1] is changed to area to differ it from R . Illustration of Equations (1) – (3) is given in Figure 1 only for two area i and j .

Figure 1. Model of connected area ($N_A = 2$), where each area has its own S, I, R components, whose relations specified by a_i, b_i, N_i for intra-area and μ_{ij}^X for inter-area.

It can be seen from Figure 7 that area i has its own $S, I,$ and R components, which can also interact with another similar components in area j through μ_{ij}^X parameters. The last parameters could be static or changed with time to represent time-dependent mobility.

2 Implementation

Equations (1) – (3) and Figure 1 are implemented using JavaScript (JS) to create a in-house software [3], whose user interface (UI) is shown in Figure 2. The software is available to test [4].

Figure 2. The in-house software with UI elements: input parameters (I), control buttons (B), visualisation area (V), node of a region (R), and SIR charts for each region (C).

In the input parameters there are seven different section with keywords, TSIM, NSIR, ABXX, MUSX, MUIX, MURX, and XYZD. The first parameter TSIM is for simulation time, which is actually still in arbitrary unit until there are the real data. NSIR stands for the initial number of people in each category (suceptible, infected, recovered), where number of lines indicates number of regions, which are five as shown in Figure 2

```
NSIR
099 001 000
100 000 000
099 001 000
100 000 000
100 000 000
```

The above input tells us that 0th region has 99 suceptible, 1 infected, and 0 recovered people as initial condition, while the 4th region has 100, 0, and 0. The 0th and 2nd regions are for city with initial infection while the others (1st, 3rd, and 4th) are for region without infection in the beginning but, they can get infection through the mobility of people from other region, which is the spatial aspect that must be also considered. The next section is for ABXX which stands for a and b parameters in Equations (1) and (2), where line i is for region i as follow

```
ABXX
0.25 0.25
0.25 0.25
0.25 0.10
0.25 0.10
0.25 0.10
```

The first two regions have the parameter of non-epidemic case, while the rests have of epidemic case. According to NSIR input section the 1st, 3rd, and 4th will not change from their initial condition since initial infection is zero. But if they get the infection from the other region, then the final results will be different. The next input section is MUSX, which is given as follow

```
MUSX
```

```

0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00

```

where it relates susceptible in region i or S_i with susceptible in region j or S_j as shown in the last two terms in previous Equation (1). In general $\mu_{ij}^S \neq \mu_{ji}^S$ or it can be function of time, e.g. for commuter of Bogor and Jakarta, which can be

$$\mu_{ij}^S = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq t < 0.25, \\ 0.1, & 0.25 \leq t < 0.75, \\ 0, & 0.75 \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

for from region j to i in the day and

$$\mu_{ji}^S = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq t < 0.25, \\ 0.1, & 0.6 \leq t < 0.9, \\ 0, & 0.9 \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

from region i to j in the night. Time step $\Delta t = 1$ is equal to one day or 24 hours. In the providing input all components are still zero indicate that there is no mobility at all. For the sections MUIX and MURX the input parameters are the same as for MUSX.

MUIX

```

0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00

```

MURX

```

0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00

```

And if the assumptions in Equation (5) and (6) are used, it should be also the same for MUIX (mobility of infected people) and MURX (mobility for recovered people). It could be not the same if there is some mechanism to detect the people while leaving from or entering in a region.

And the last section of input parameters is position and size of the region

XYZD

```

0.20 0.20 0.00 0.15
0.20 0.80 0.00 0.10
0.80 0.80 0.00 0.08
0.80 0.20 0.00 0.12
0.50 0.50 0.00 0.20

```

The coordinates are x , y , and z , where the last column is for the size or diameter D of a region.

3 Results and discussion

There are several scenarios that is simulated using the in-house JS application [4], such as two isolated regions and two regions with various types of connections.

3.1 Two isolated regions.

Simulation parameters are shown on the right, where the larger region (region 0) has epidemic case and the smaller region (region 1) has non-epidemic case. Since the parameters μ_{ij}^X , with $X = S, I, R$, are all zero, then the region will behave as there is no interaction between them. For the two regions the R_0 is 2.5 and 1, respectively.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the in-house application for the case of two regions.

There is no interesting feature to discuss for this scenario. It can represent a lockdown case.

```

TSIM 100
NSIR
199 001 000
099 001 000
ABXX
0.25 0.10
0.25 0.25
MUSX
0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00
MUIX
0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00
MURX
0.00 0.00
0.00 0.00
XYZD
0.20 0.80 0.00 0.20
0.80 0.80 0.00 0.10
    
```

3.2 Two regions with connection: one-way mobility ($0 \rightarrow 1$)

As shown in the parameter box on the right, people can move from region 0 (larger one) to the smaller region (smaller one) with $\mu_{10}^S = \mu_{10}^I = \mu_{10}^R = 0.01$, but not otherwise. In the beginning of the simulation $N_0 = 200$ and $N_1 = 100$, but at the end, $N_0 = 69.6$ and $N_1 = 223.3$ as shown in Figure 4. The total population reduces a little bit due to the calculation method in solving the differential equation from Equations (1) – (3).

Figure 4. Screenshot of the in-house application for the case of two regions with connection of the type of one-way mobility.

```

TSIM 100
NSIR
199 001 000
099 001 000
ABXX
0.25 0.10
0.25 0.25
MUSX
0.00 0.00
0.01 0.00
MUIX
0.00 0.00
0.01 0.00
MURX
0.00 0.00
0.01 0.00
XYZD
0.20 0.80 0.00 0.20
0.80 0.80 0.00 0.10
    
```

3.3 Two regions with connection: two-ways mobility ($0 \leftrightarrow 1$) averaging

In this scenario people can move from region 0 (larger one) to region 1 (smaller one) and vice versa with the same mobility, $\mu_{10}^S = \mu_{10}^I = \mu_{10}^R = 0.01$ and $\mu_{01}^S = \mu_{01}^I = \mu_{01}^R = 0.01$. The results is shown in Figure 5, where the larger region still has epidemic case, but the smaller one exhibits pandemic-like case but without clear peak of the infection.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the in-house application for the case of two regions with connection of the type of two-way mobility.

Since the mobility is the same in the end population of the two regions tend to be equal.

```

TSIM 100
NSIR
199 001 000
099 001 000
ABXX
0.25 0.10
0.25 0.25
MUSX
0.00 0.01
0.01 0.00
MUIX
0.00 0.01
0.01 0.00
MURX
0.00 0.01
0.01 0.00
XYZD
0.20 0.80 0.00 0.20
0.80 0.80 0.00 0.10
    
```

3.4 Two regions with connection: two-ways mobility ($0 \leftrightarrow 1$) in equilibrium

We can also set μ_{ij}^X that will maintain relatively population in each region. One of the way is to set it proportional to the popution of its region as shown in the parameter box on the right, which is $\mu_{01}^X = 2\mu_{10}^X$, with $X = S, I, R$.

Figure 6. Screenshot of the in-house application for the case of two regions with connection of the type of two-way mobility but not equal to mantain each region initial population.

It can be seen from Figure 6 that in the beginning of the simulation $N_0 = 200$ and $N_1 = 100$, and the the end $N_0 = 195.6$ and $N_1 = 98.4$, which shows an equilibrium condition.

3.5 Two regions with connection: two-ways mobility ($0 \leftrightarrow 1$) drain out

Now we want to simulate when $\mu_{01}^X < \mu_{10}^X$ with parameters are shown on the right box.

Figure 7. Screenshot of the in-house application for the case of two regions with connection of the type of two-way mobility for drain-out case.

In this scenario the mobility out of region 0 is larger than into it, as seen in Figure 7. The two regions have initial population of 200 and 100, respectively, and then 102.0 and 191.5 as the final population.

3.6 Discussion

Recalling the parameters a and b for each region, we can say that it depends on the region structure, e.g. province, regency, city, village, etc, which limit the interaction or support interaction of the people. In the modern city an infected person can travel in a longer distance than the one in the village due to transportation infrastructure. And the first will interact with more people than the second.

To clear readability we will change the symbol as follow

$$\mu_{ji}^S \equiv \mu_{i \rightarrow j}^S, \quad (7)$$

which describes mobility from region i to region j for suceptible person S . The notation in Equation (7) will also be used for infected and recovered people, I and R , respectively.

From scenario in equilibrium or balance commuter following relation is used

$$\mu_{ji}^X N_i = \mu_{ij}^X N_j, \quad (8)$$

which assures that each region population remains the same. In Equation (8), X is for S, I, R .

Tabel 1. Initial and final population of the two regions with different scenario and what each scenario represents in the nearly similar real condition, where region 0 is larger in area and higher in population than region 1.

Scenario	Parameters		Initial population		Final population		Error	$\mu_{0 \rightarrow 1}^X$	$\mu_{1 \rightarrow 0}^X$	Nearly similar real condition	Epidemic
	a_1, b_1	a_2, b_2	S_0, I_0, R_0	S_1, I_1, R_1	S_0, I_0, R_0	S_1, I_1, R_1					
3.1	0.25, 0.1	0.25, 0.25	199, 1, 0	99, 1, 0	22.6, 1.3, 169.7	87.2, 0.1, 12.5	6.6	0	0	Two isolated cities $0 \cdot 1$	0
3.2	0.25, 0.1	0.25, 0.25	199, 1, 0	99, 1, 0	8.3, 0.5, 60.9	123.2, 0.2, 99.9	7	0.01	0	Evacuation $0 \rightarrow 1$	0
3.3	0.25, 0.1	0.25, 0.25	199, 1, 0	99, 1, 0	34.6, 2.0, 116.1	59.7, 0.2, 81.4	6	0.01	0.01	Equal population policy $0 \leftrightarrow 1$	0, 1
3.4	0.25, 0.1	0.25, 0.25	199, 1, 0	99, 1, 0	41.6, 2.4, 151.6	32.0, 0.2, 66.2	6	0.01	0.02	Balance commuter $0 \leftrightarrow 1$	0, 1
3.5	0.25, 0.1	0.25, 0.25	199, 1, 0	99, 1, 0	29.7, 1.8, 70.5	83.1, 0.3, 108.0	6.6	0.02	0.01	Big holiday $0 \leftrightarrow 1$	0, 1

Epidemic is defined when R curve more than S curve in ratio of current population in the same region. This definition is still debatable and subject to change after further discussion. Following results are found.

1. Scenario of two isolation regions shows independent results and does not require further discussion.
2. Scenario of evacuation still depends on the rate of mobility. If the source region is in the epidemic state, there is no guarantee that the destination region will be also in the same or better state.
3. Scenario of equal population policy, which could be initiated for better living quality assuming equal region infrastructure, will also propagate the epidemic state from the source region to the destination region.
4. Scenario of balance commuter will also propagate the epidemic state from source region to destination region, but milder than the previous scenario.
5. Scenario of big holiday is the worst since the mobility from source region to destination region is higher than the other way. Such event in Indonesia is Mudik Lebaran.

Longer simulation time and more regions are subjects to investigate in the next discussion.

4 Summaries

From this discussion it can be summarized that the spatial aspect added to SIR model is very interesting to discuss. Only interaction between two regions are simulated. Five scenario are tested and only two shows the desired results that the infection does not spread and does not make the two regions in the same epidemic state. Simulation with more regions requires better plan in analyzing the parameters since more data are produced.

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